

Language as a medium for New Normal in Naga culture

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“Seeing oneself from outside oneself as if one was another self”
- Ngugi Wa Thiong’o

Introduction to the ancient and contemporary Naga culture (From Morungs to educational institutions to Mass media)

In this paper I will be discussing on impact of educational institutions, mass media, books, journals etc. on Naga culture. How it has affected our Naga culture(language) both positively as well as negatively through amalgamation of ‘other’ culture. It is necessary for the contemporary generation to retain and understand our native culture (language), as language is considered as one of the fundamental aspects of our identity.

Before discussing the topic, Firstly, let me briefly elaborate, how the ancient Naga culture was passed-on from one generation to the other. The ancient Naga unmarried males go to the ‘Morungs’ which is considered as the cardinal learning institution during the time. It is a place where the young boys of the Naga society go to learn about the social practices and believes of the society from the elders. It is also considered as the dormitory of the young male youths. The pattern of ‘Morung’ differs from tribe to tribe, they are known by different names in different tribes Rahang-ki in Zeme, Kiang-Yam in Yimkiung, Arju in Ao, Kichuki in Angami etc. This young youths are taught in their own dialects at the ‘Morung’.

Prior to the advent of colonization in the Naga Hills, the Nagas were believed to have had a very diverse and a rich culture, spoke ‘Central tibeto-burmese language’. But, with the advent of the Britishers in the Naga Hills in the mid-19th century and the amalgamation of the culture with the colonial culture, this practice of teaching in local dialects were impinged. Since, the colonizers taught the locals in English in order to communicate with them. In 1886 there were already 8 Primary schools in 8 different villages. One of the oldest schools in Nagaland is Clark Memorial Higher Secondary School, which was setup as a mission training school on the 11th of April 1895 at Impur Village, Mokokchung district by the American Missionary, now it has been upgrade from school to Higher Secondary.

With the advent of the colonization entailed the advent of education in the Naga society. Education has many positive impacts on the society, but fundamentally there are two major factors which encouraged education in the Naga society which is still prevalent in the contemporary Naga society.

Firstly, in order to secure a job especially in the government sector, one needs to be educated to a certain standard, without which it was not possible to secure any job. Secondly, when it comes to religion (Christianity) as well, in order to understand the Bible, one has to know how to read and write. Without having the basic ability to read and write it would not be possible to understand the Bible in its true sense on our own. For these two cardinal factors education in English became one of the pivotal means of learning.

With the advancement in the usage of technology and the impact of pandemic on the Naga society, divergent of the Naga culture from the native culture has also built up even more. Mass media has extensive impact on the society not only on just the Naga society but it also impacts the whole cosmos at large. It not only covers political, social, environmental, etc. aspects but most importantly influences the younger generations which are very much active in the technological usage.

Herman and Chomsky states that

“The culture and ideology fostered in this globalization process relate largely to “lifestyle” themes and goods and their acquisition; and they tend to weaken any sense of community helpful to civic life.”¹

We will be discussing in the following paragraphs how educational institutions, mass media, books, journals etc. Impacts our society. What can be done in to order retain our identity as a Naga and to maintain the equilibrium between the Naga culture and the other cultures and eventually resulting to ‘New Normal’ of the Naga culture.

¹ Herman and Chomsky, *Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media* (The Bodley Head, 2008) Introduction, p-18.

Variations of Naga dialects and its evolution in brief.

There are 16 districts in Nagaland, as listed in the table below **Table 1.**

Table 1

Districts in Nagaland			
1. Chümoukedima	2. Dimapur	3. Kiphire	4. Kohima
5. Longleng	6. Mokokchung	7. Mon	8. Niuland
9. Noklak	10. Peren	11. Phek	12. Shamator
13. Tuensang	14. Tseminyü	15. Wokha	16. Zünheboto

There are officially 17 Naga tribes recognized by the government of Nagaland **Table 2,**

Table 2

Tribes of Nagaland			
1. Angami	2. Ao	3. Chakesang	4. Chang
5. Khiamnungan	6. Kuki	7. Konyak	8. Kachari
9. Lotha	10. Phom	11. Pochury	12. Rengma
13. Sumi	14. Sangtam	15. Tikhir	16. Yimkhiung
17. Zeliang			

Each tribe speaks different dialects in order to communicate with each other. Among this 17 different Naga tribes, the variations of the dialect spoken by the same tribes varies according to the geographical differences.

For instance, take the case of “Zeliang” tribe, essentially “Zeliang” is a concoction of two sub-tribes i.e. Zeme and Liangmei they are settled in a very wide geographical settlement across the North-Eastern part of India such as Nagaland, Manipur, Assam etc. In all these states, we can find “Zeliang” settlers and they do speak Zeliang dialect for communication among themselves. This is not only the case, even the intra state dialect differs from one district to the other district, which sometimes creates difficulties in conveying the messages across to each others.

In Nagaland, there are 90 Recognized and 20 Unrecognized villages which comes under Peren district such Peren, Jalukie, Gaili, Heningkunglwa, Punglwa, Mhai-namtsi etc. They all do speak Zeliang dialect to convey their message across to each other but, because of the geographical differences, their dialects are as well are affected. There are many minor differences such as some words are spelled or pronounced the same way, but the accent of the word differs from each region. There are some significant differences in their dialect among themselves as well, where the words are completely spelled different and pronounced differently.

It is not only the case for “Zeliang” tribe, but it has similarities with other tribes as well. Basically, under the 17 recognized tribes by the government of Nagaland, there are many other sub-tribes and sub-dialects spoken by the people of Nagaland.

English is the official language of Nagaland, but the language that we use for our general conversation among the different tribes is “Nagamese”.

“Nagamese...is very easy to pick up and with a little application can be spoken perfectly. It is, moreover, an excellent vehicle for the expression of Naga turns of speech and thought.”²

In fact, it is more or less a colonized language. Although there is no concrete prove as to its exact inception of it, but it is believed that numerous forms of interaction between the plainsmen (especially those Assamese neighbors) and the Nagas, such as migration, trade, services, marriage, etc., must have led to the development of Nagamese as a universal language.

² Hutton, J H, *The Angami Nagas.* (Macmillan & Co. Ltd., London) 1921, p. 327.

All this variations and difference usually starts with a gradual pace and according to the displacements of the people from their native dialect speaking community. Just as, I have mention about the variations of dialects among the “Zeliang” tribes as well. Due to various reasons such as trade, services, marriage, etc., people are displaced from their native dialect speaking community. Both during the past and the present the main reason for the displacement is for survival.

At present one of the most common reason for displacement is, pursuing a better lifestyle and moving into the cosmopolitan cities where the wages or salaries are much better in comparison to the rural areas. This is also one of the pivotal causes of amalgamation of our native dialects.

Language being the fundamental component of cultural identity.

Language is a set of systematically structured communication, which is used by humans to communicate with each other. It does not necessarily confine to speech and gesture but also covers signing and writing as well. One of the vital parts in a language which has to be regarded appropriately is the grammar of the language without which the whole meaning would collapse. There are enormous number of languages across the globe depending from one geographical area to the other, they all have their own way of expressing themselves in various ways and forms.

There are different kinds of language for different society, activities, profession etc. So, depending on the kind of group a person is involved in, they use the appropriate language. A person can be a member of different groups and can use different language according to their participation in the group. A supporter of wrestling will have their own way of cheering their players. This kind of cheering can give the supporter a sense of oneness and belonging to a particular group.

Similarly, although there are people of diverse kinds and features, the use of our mother tongue or our native dialect gives us the sense of oneness. To put it into perspective, when someone say, that they belong to a particular community ‘X’, then it is evident that they would be essentially speaking in ‘X’ dialect. No matter where ever they are, they would be identified as from the ‘X’ community. Although just being able to speak the same dialect while communicating with the ‘X’ community does not necessarily mean they are from the ‘X’ community.

Languages are both acquired naturally and learned formally.

“We are born crying, but those cries herald the first stirrings of language.”³

The early stage of learning starts from the time we are born crying. Children born in a particular family of a particular community acquires the language that they are born into. Learning of language is considered as the product of the ability to reason in humans. Rene Descartes in his ‘*Discourse on the Method*’ said “*the brutes have less reason than man, but that they have none at all: for we see that very little is required to enable a person to speak.*”⁴

Human being as a ‘*rational soul*’ and even the stupidest person is able to learn language. He implies that learning is basically the ability of human being to reason and also it needs very less afford to do so.

Besides, learning our mother tongue we tend to learn other languages as well from different sources such as educational institutions, mass media, books, journals etc. This are the most influential factors in learning of new language. The first source of learning new language besides our mother tongue or local language comes from educational institutions, where we are taught in English. Secondly, one of the most extensive influential sources is the mass media which has huge impact on our present generation in teaching new language.

Impact of educational institutions and mass media on Naga culture (New Normal)

If we consider any kind of society around the globe, there is always the dominating class and the oppressed class which is inevitable in the functioning of the society. It is a well-known fact that the dominant class (which is generally the capitalist) has the higher position in making any decisions in the society. While the oppressed class are more or less bound to follow the decisions of the dominant class.

“The mass media serve as a system for communicating messages and symbols to the general populace. It is their function to amuse, entertain, and inform, and to inculcate individuals with the values, beliefs, and codes of behavior that will integrate them into the institutional structures of the larger society. In a world of concentrated wealth and major conflicts of class interest, to fulfil this role requires systematic propaganda.”⁵

³ Robert C. Berwick, Noam Chomsky, *Why Only Us Language and Evolution* (The MIT Press Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England, 2016) Chp-1, p-1.

⁴ Rene Descartes, *A Discourse on the Method* (Duke Classics, 2012) Part-V, p-47.

⁵ Herman and Chomsky, *Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media* (The Bodley Head, 2008) Chp-1, p-1.

Mass media and education has both negative and positive influence in the society. It not only provides us with various kinds of entertainments but also knowingly or unknowingly imbibe in us social norms and behaviors. Those capitalists and the ruling class are more or less the in-charge of the both education and mass media.

In Noam Chomsky's own words "*Education is a system of imposed ignorance*", by which he does not completely despise education. Children at the learning stage are naturally very creative and has great imaginary ability to build their world. But once they start formal education, they are bound to learn basically what is taught to them according to the academic curriculums of the educational institutions.

He is not the only person who has supported this idea but, Albert Einstein who is also considered as one of the brightest minds in the world and the pioneer of

Relativity Theory also talks about how his schooling has almost impaired his Mathematics and physics, but recovered on leaving the school.

According to Noam Chomsky in his book "*Manufacturing Consent: The Political economy of the Mass Media*" written in collaboration with Edward S. Herman, he says that with the unequal distribution of wealth entails the bias portrayals of the dominant class in the society by the media. Although the medias objective is to be non-bias against any class of the society, but they are only the puppet of those in-charge of the media and the educational institutions. Generally, it is the government and the capitalist who has the power to manipulate both the educational institutions and the mass media.

Since, most of the higher position occupied in the government, media, education system etc. with the help of the corporates and they tend to have the power to make decisions for the functioning of the society, to what kind of education to be imparted on the future generations and also how the mass media should function.

*"But entertainment has the merit not only of being better suited to helping sell goods; it is an effective vehicle for hidden ideological messages."*⁶

For Noam Chomsky, there are three cardinal claims that influences the society through mass media, is that it covers those stories which would benefit the dominant class, in the process they would gain advertisement revenues and finally, experts would provide their opinions in favor of the dominant class.

Now, when we contextualized it with our Naga culture as well. One can clearly see how mass media and educational institutions has had huge influence on the society. Especially, with pandemic paralyzing the normal functioning of the society. It has in many ways forced us to isolate ourselves from the society. Due to which most of us has become even more active in using social media and our physical interaction has decreased significantly. Our present generation is undeniably very much active in different ways in mass media, which has huge impact on the Naga society. There are now significant number of populations who are not confident to speak in their own mother tongue but fluent enough in other language such as English and Nagamese. There has been schools and colleges where different languages are being taught to the students such as Hindi, Korean, Mandarin etc. This are some major influences of the mass media and educational institutions in the Naga Society.

One of the most commonly spoken and understood language among the younger generation in our contemporary Naga society is English besides Nagamese which is also more or less a colonized language. They are more comfortable in communicating in English rather than being comfortable in their own Native Language.

What has really happened is that, our native language has been sidelined extensively and is considered as an alien language to them. While the new language (English) is considered as their Normal Language. So, for the contemporary younger generation of the Naga Society English is their New Normal language.

Conclusion

Language being essentially a cardinal part of our identity. As stated by Noam Chomsky, the influence on language through different means such as educational institutions, mass media, books, journals etc. has led to the evolution of Naga culture into a more complex culture. This 'New Culture' tend to have overshadowed our native culture, which entails the state of confusion for the native Naga culture.

There is no doubt that, there are many positive influences of educational institutions and mass media on the Naga society. It has not only aided in providing job security and also contributed in religious growth. Without education it is almost impossible to find government jobs or be it private sector as well. So also, without education, one cannot really understand what our religion (Christianity) teaching are in its true sense.

Likewise, it also has its negative influences on Naga culture. With growing rate of educated population through educational institutions and mass media influences, the amalgamation of our Naga culture with the other culture has really created a confusion on our native culture. The contemporary younger generation from our

⁶ Herman and Chomsky, *Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media* (The Bodley Head, 2008) Introduction, p-18.

society (Naga) has become confused by considering what is the amalgamated culture as their native culture and not only that, they considered their native culture as alien to them.

Therefore, after considering all the above paragraphs, it is of my opinion that in this 21st century the world has become a global village with the advancements of technology. It is non-viable to have a pure culture without any kind of influence over it leading to its evolution. So, what one can do is, one has to adapt with the evolution of culture but at the same time it should not let the evolution process completely dissolve the essence of our native culture. Basically, one has to create a balance between the new culture and the native culture.

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